

Multi Camera Robust Diagnosis of Fundus Diseases: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Multi Camera Robust Diagnosis of Fundus Diseases

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

MuCaRD

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Accurate classification of retinal diseases—such as glaucoma and diabetic retinopathy—is critical for preventing irreversible vision loss. Although existing screening solutions based on fundus images (e.g., LumineticsCore by Digital Diagnostics) show promise, they often struggle with “unseen” fundus camera images not included in their development. This limitation stems primarily from the continuous influx of new camera models and the varying adoption rates of certain devices.

Considering these issues, we propose the Multi-Camera Robust Classification of Fundus Diseases (MuCaRD) challenge, designed to foster AI models that remain reliable across diverse and previously unseen cameras. The challenge consists of two tasks. 1) Classification of Glaucoma and Diabetic Retinopathy for Unseen Fundus Cameras : creating a generalized model robust to any camera type, and 2) Classification of Glaucoma and Diabetic Retinopathy with Few-Shot Test Time Adaptation : building a model capable of adapting to new or rare cameras with only a small number of sample images. Two datasets form the backbone of this challenge: the NIH-funded AIREADI dataset, comprising images from Optomed Aurora, Eidon, and Mediwhale, and the Mediwhale dataset, which includes Optomed Aurora, Mediwork FC162, Topcon NW400, Optos Ultra Wide Fundus, and Canon CR2. In Task 1, the Mediwhale dataset will serve as the primary source for training and testing, while the AIREADI dataset will be used for validation. In Task 2, the Mediwhale dataset will again serve as the main training and testing resource, while the AIREADI dataset will provide both validation and support sets in validation and test stages. Through these tasks, the MuCaRD challenge aims to ensure that AI-driven screening models for fundus diseases remain robust, adaptable, and accurate, irrespective of the camera source.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Fundus, Multi Camera, Glaucoma, Diabetic Retinopathy

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

Traditional research on fundus image analysis has largely focused on classifying diseases or identifying biomarkers within a single, fixed dataset. However, in real clinical and product-level environments, AI models must maintain robust performance even when encountering entirely new camera systems. This challenge takes a step beyond simple disease classification by emphasizing adaptability to multiple camera types. Such an approach reflects the practical realities of medical AI, which needs to succeed not only in a controlled research setting but also in diverse, real-world clinical and commercial applications. This consideration of actual usage environments—where camera devices may vary or continue to evolve—is a key novelty that distinguishes this challenge from prior research efforts.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The MuCaRD challenge comprises two core tasks: (1) Classification of Glaucoma and Diabetic Retinopathy for Unseen Fundus Cameras, and (2) Classification of Glaucoma and Diabetic Retinopathy with Few-Shot Test-Time Adaptation. In both tasks, participants tackle two separate binary classification problems: distinguishing normal from abnormal (referable) for glaucoma, and normal from abnormal (referable) for diabetic retinopathy. We focus on these two diseases because they are among the most common ophthalmological conditions. For scoring, results are computed separately for glaucoma and diabetic retinopathy, and then averaged to produce each participant's overall score.

In Task 1, participants focus on building models that predict robustly on unseen fundus images. They will train on approximately 400 fundus images captured by Mediwhale's NW400 camera. During the validation phase, around 200 Optomed Aurora images from AIREADI, plus 200 images each from Mediwork FC162, Optos Ultra Wide Fundus, and Canon CR2 will be used to assess model performance. Importantly, participants will submit their models through the CodaLab platform, and the validation dataset will remain hidden. In the test phase, roughly 200 images each from Mediwhale's Aurora, Mediwork FC162, Optos Ultra Wide Fundus, and Canon CR2 will be evaluated on how well the models handle entirely unseen cameras. Key metrics for this task include the area under the ROC curve (AUROC) and the area under the precision–recall curve (AUPRC).

Task 2 concentrates on adapting to new cameras with only a small number of additional new camera images. The training, validation, and test set configurations, as well as the CodaLab-based evaluation process (with no data leakage), mirror those in Task 1. However, during both the validation and test phases, a support set comprising images from the AIREADI and Mediwhale datasets will be provided online through the organizers' evaluation server. Participants can use these few-shot images to perform on-the-fly adaptation. The evaluation metrics remain the same as in Task 1.

Through these two tasks, the MuCaRD challenge seeks to advance AI solutions that can be seamlessly integrated into various clinical settings, ultimately enhancing the reliability and scalability of medical imaging diagnostics.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

No

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

We propose a 2 Hours workshop, designed to share tips and techniques from challenge participants and feature presentations by medical imaging experts, prominent physicians, and the organizing committee. We plan to have four speakers in total—three from the organizing committee and one external guest.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We expect approximately 60 teams in total for the two tasks at the MuCaRD Challenge, drawing on participation trends from both recent and comparable past events. For instance, MICCAI MMAC (2023) Challenge and UWF4DR (2024) Challenge each involved around 100 participants, with about 30 teams per task. Moreover, the GAMMA(2021) Challenge attracted 70 teams.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

We plan to compile the challenge results into a summary paper and conduct additional validation using Mediwhale's internal data. Because this dataset includes images from diverse camera manufacturers such as Topcon, Canon, Carl Zeiss, Baxter, Eyerobo, and Remidio, the paper will evaluate a wide range of analysis and is expected to make a significant impact on both researchers and industry.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

We have decided on a 2 hours format, and will require a typical presentation setup, including a microphone, monitor, projectors, and a suitable space for the presentations.

TASK 1: Classification of Glaucoma and Diabetic Retinopathy for Unseen Fundus Cameras

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Accurate classification of retinal diseases—such as glaucoma and diabetic retinopathy—is critical for preventing irreversible vision loss. Although existing screening solutions based on fundus images (e.g., LumineticsCore by Digital Diagnostics) show promise, they often struggle with “unseen” fundus camera images not included in their development. This limitation arises from the continuous influx of new camera models and the varying adoption rates of certain devices. Considering these issues, we propose the Multi-Camera Robust Classification of Fundus Diseases (MuCaRD) challenge, which encourages AI models to work reliably with diverse, previously unseen cameras.

For Task 1, "Classification of Glaucoma and Diabetic Retinopathy on Unseen Fundus Cameras," the goal is to create a generalized model robust to any camera type. Two datasets support this effort: the NIH-funded AIREADI dataset, which includes images from Optomed Aurora and Eidon, and the Mediwhale dataset, which contains images from Optomed Aurora, Mediwork FC162, Topcon NW400, Optos Ultra Wide Fundus, and Canon CR2. In this task, the Mediwhale dataset will serve as the primary source for training and testing, while the AIREADI dataset will be used for validation.

To maintain fairness and ensure that the validation and test datasets remain completely unseen by participants, the challenge will be conducted on the CodaLab platform. Participants will submit both their inference code and trained model weights, which the organizers will then run on a secure evaluation server. Performance is assessed using AUROC and AUPRC as the key metrics. Through this process, participants are encouraged to develop a truly camera-agnostic, generalized classification model for glaucoma and diabetic retinopathy.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Fundus, Robustness, Multi Camera, Deep learning, zero shot

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Aaron Y. Lee – Department of Ophthalmology, University of Washington, Seattle, Washington

Cecilia S. Lee – Department of Ophthalmology, University of Washington, Seattle, Washington

Dongha Lee – Department of Artificial Intelligence, Yonsei University

Dongjin Nam – Mediwhale; Yonsei University College of Medicine

Geunyoung Lee – Mediwhale

Heeju Ko – Mediwhale

Hyeonmin Kim – Mediwhale

Junseok Park – Mediwhale; Seoul National University College of Medicine

Jungkyung Cho – Mediwhale; Seoul National University College of Medicine

Kai Tzu-iunn Ong – Department of Artificial Intelligence, Yonsei University

Sahil Thakur – Mediwhale

Soojin Hwang – Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Pohang University of Science and Technology

Sungyeon Kim – Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Pohang University of Science and Technology

Taegeun Yoo – Mediwhale

Tyler Hyungtaek Rim – Mediwhale; Duke-NUS Medical School; Singapore Eye Research Institute

Wonhwa Kim – Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Pohang University of Science and Technology

Yongseok Lee – Mediwhale; Yonsei University College of Medicine

Yunnie Cho – Mediwhale; Seoul National University College of Medicine

Yeonwoo Jung – Mediwhale; Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Pohang University of Science and Technology

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Hyeonmin Kim, Mediwhale, kjven0625@mediwhale.com

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

CodaLab (<https://codalab.lisn.upsaclay.fr/>).

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

The challenge platform will be set up once the proposal is accepted.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May not participate

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We intend to award certificates to the top three teams for each task

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The top three performing methods will be publicly announced, and participants will be required to submit documentation detailing their code and methodology. They must also demonstrate reproducibility by providing the datasets used.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Each participant may publish their own papers. However, only the first authors and corresponding authors of the winning teams will be included in the challenge summary paper published by the organizers.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Participants will add their training models and image preprocessing methods to the model.py provided by the organizers and submit it along with the model weights to CodaLab. We encourage the use of MONAI and recommend submitting the code in the form of a MONAI bundle whenever possible to enhance reusability.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

During the validation phase, participants may submit up to two times per day over approximately two months. In the test phase, three submissions will be permitted, and the organizers will select the best result among them. In both phases, participants will submit their inference code and trained model weights for evaluation on the organizers' evaluation server, where the validation and test sets remain completely isolated.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Registration period: April 1 - June 1, 2025

Release date of training set: June 1, 2025

model for Validation submission period June 1, - August 15, 2025

model for Test submission period: August 15 - August 23, 2025

Winner announcement date: August 30, 2025

Report submission period (for Winner): August 30 - September 15, 2025

Release date of the results: challenge day (October 6 or 10, 2025)

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

AIREADI has already received IRB approval. The AIREADI project is funded by the NIH under award number 1OT2OD032644. The IRB approval for AIREADI can be found here:

https://docs.aireadi.org/v1/Approval_STUDY00016228_Lee_initial.pdf. In addition, another study that will be used in conjunction is currently under IRB review, and all data collection will begin only after IRB approval. We plan to collect data between March and June 2025.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)

- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY (Attribution)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

we will publish the metric calculation code for ranking evaluation. This code will be made available on GitHub and accessible to everyone.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participants are encouraged to publicly share their code to GitHub, and it is mandatory for winning teams to do so.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Some of the challenge organizers are employees of Mediwhale. Once the test phase begins, only the challenge organizers, including those from other institutions, will have access to the test dataset.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Screening

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort includes individuals with diabetic retinopathy and/or glaucoma who have undergone fundoscopic imaging using multiple fundus cameras. Incorporating a variety of commercially available cameras reflects the final biomedical application scenario and ensures broader applicability. Both the World Health Organization (WHO) and the U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) recommend regular eye exams for these conditions, underscoring the importance of applicability across diverse imaging devices.

(<https://www.who.int/europe/publications/i/item/9789289055321>, <https://www.uspreventiveservicestaskforce.org/uspstf/recommendation/primary-open-angle-glaucoma-screening>).

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort consists of a dataset collected from primary care centers and hospitals in South Korea and Cambodia. This dataset includes retinal images of patients diagnosed with glaucoma and/or diabetic retinopathy. The images were captured using a variety of fundus cameras, including the Topcon TRC-NW400, Optomed Aurora handheld fundus camera, Mediworks FC162, Optos Ultra-Wide Fundus, and Canon CR2 models.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Color Fundus Photography(CFP)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Each Color Fundus Photograph is captured with either the optic disk or the fovea as the center

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Data from the AI-READI project ensures balanced representation across disease severity, race/ethnicity, and gender, thereby enhancing the dataset's generalizability and equity. Additionally, the Mediwhale dataset includes patients aged 20 and above from local clinics and hospitals in South Korea and Cambodia, regardless of gender.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The AI-READI project collects data from multiple sites across the United States, ensuring broad representation across disease severity, race/ethnicity, and gender. This includes various data modalities relevant to diabetes management and retinal health. Meanwhile, the Mediwhale dataset consists of fundus images acquired from local clinics and large hospitals in East Asia—specifically South Korea and Cambodia. These retinal images form the basis for diagnosing and studying conditions like glaucoma and diabetic retinopathy in both the target and challenge cohorts.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Screening glaucoma, diabetic retinopathy

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Consistency,Robustness,Sensitivity,Specificity

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Optomed aurora handheld fundus camera

Topcon NW400 fundus camera

Mediworks FC162 camera

Optos Ultra Wide Fundus

Canon CR2 cameras

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Fundus images were captured by experienced ophthalmologists following standardized imaging protocols.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The data for the AI-READI (AI Ready and Equitable Atlas for Diabetes Insights) project was acquired from three major sites across the United States, involving the recruitment of 4,000 participants. These centers ensure a balanced representation across disease severity, race/ethnicity, and gender, thereby enhancing the dataset's generalizability and equity.

Additionally, the Mediwhale dataset comprises retinal images obtained from multiple local clinics and large hospitals in East Asia, including South Korea and Cambodia. Due to Mediwhale's anonymization and data export policies, the dataset sources are limited to South Korea and Cambodia within the East Asian region.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data were collected by specialized ophthalmologists with over five years of experience.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

In this challenge, a "case" refers to a single color fundus photograph along with any associated metadata including the camera name and reference labels for diabetic retinopathy and glaucoma (e.g., presence or absence of each disease). The algorithm must generate a classification for each case, which is then compared against these

reference labels.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The entire dataset includes approximately 400 images from the NW400 camera for training. During the validation phase, 1,000 images will be used—200 each from Topcon NW400, Optomed Aurora, Mediworks FC162, Optos Ultra Wide Fundus, and Canon CR2 cameras. An identical distribution of 1,000 images will be applied for the test phase, also split evenly among these five cameras. The positive rates for glaucoma and diabetic retinopathy are 7% and 6%, respectively. The training and test datasets will come from Mediwhale, while the validation dataset will be composed of both AI-READI and Mediwhale data.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The challenge aims to replicate a real-world production environment where variations in camera manufacturers lead to differences in color profiles and image quality. Recognizing that models may be discontinued or replaced (e.g., the transition from Topcon NW400 to NW500), it is crucial to ensure that new models can adapt to these changes. This scenario is common across all data modalities, underscoring the importance of incorporating diverse camera data.

To address this, the dataset includes approximately 400 NW400 images for training—mirroring the training set size of the REFUGE1 challenge. For validation and testing, each set comprises 1,000 images, distributed evenly across five camera models: Topcon NW400, Optomed Aurora, Mediworks FC162, Optos Ultra Wide Fundus, and Canon CR2 (200 images per model). This balanced distribution is designed to enhance model robustness and ensure better generalization to various imaging devices.

Participants are also encouraged to leverage external open datasets, such as Justrags and REFUGE, to bolster their training efforts. By maintaining diversity in the validation and test sets and encouraging the use of varied training data, this dataset reflects the development of adaptable, reliable diagnostic models suitable for production environments.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The data was primarily collected from local primary care hospitals and major hospitals in South Korea and Cambodia, ensuring that it reflects real-world conditions and distributions.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

The data was exclusively gathered from local primary care hospitals and major hospitals in South Korea and Cambodia. It is entirely novel, with no publicly available datasets utilized.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The ground truth was determined by a consensus of two experienced ophthalmologists (and a third if necessary).

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if

necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Ophthalmologists were instructed to consider diabetic retinopathy (DR) and glaucoma when reviewing CFP images.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We have two classes of annotators:

A1 - Ophthalmologists with at least five years of professional experience

A2 - Ophthalmologists with at least ten years of professional experience

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The basic annotations of the datasets were meticulously performed by two A1 annotators. If there was a disagreement in these annotations, a third annotation by A2 annotator was brought in to resolve the discrepancy. This process was consistently applied across the training, validation, and test sets to ensure uniformity and reliability in the annotations.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For personal information protection, RGB-formatted CFP images (in .PNG format) were extracted from the original DICOM files.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Since image annotations in this dataset were determined by consensus, one primary source of potential error arises when there is a disagreement between the two A1 annotators. Such discrepancies are resolved by involving an A2 annotator, but minor variability may still remain.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We will evaluate the submitted algorithms primarily using Area Under the ROC Curve (AUROC) and Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve (AUPRC) for each classification task (glaucoma vs. normal, and diabetic retinopathy vs. normal) across multiple fundus cameras. The final ranking for each team will be determined by averaging the AUROC and AUPRC scores for the two diseases.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

In addressing the challenge of class imbalance, we note that glaucoma and diabetic retinopathy each have a relatively low prevalence (about 6–7% in our dataset). While the Area Under the ROC Curve (AUROC) is a widely recognized measure that summarizes performance across all decision thresholds, it can be overly optimistic for imbalanced datasets. Therefore, we also include the Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve (AUPRC), which provides a more detailed view of how well a model identifies true positives across varying thresholds. This is particularly crucial for diseases like glaucoma and diabetic retinopathy, where missed cases can have serious clinical implications. By combining AUROC and AUPRC, as suggested by Evaluation of domain generalization and adaptation on improving model robustness to temporal dataset shift in clinical medicine (Guo et al., 2022), we balance the model's overall discriminative power with its ability to detect the smaller positive class, ensuring a more comprehensive evaluation of both general and minority-class performance.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Each submission will be evaluated on five camera subsets: Topcon NW400, Optomed Aurora, Mediworks FC162, Optos Ultra Wide, and Canon CR2. Specifically, we will compute both the AUROC and AUPRC for the glaucoma classification and the diabetic retinopathy classification tasks for each subset. We then average these two metrics to derive a single camera-specific score per disease, and finally average across diseases. The overall score for each submission is obtained by further averaging these camera-specific scores across all five subsets. Submissions will be ranked in descending order based on this final overall score.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If a submission is incomplete, it will not be counted, and participants will be allowed to resubmit. In cases of missing results, an error message will be provided, automatically notifying participants of the required elements as part of the error feedback.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Our primary objective is to ensure robust classification performance in the context of class imbalance while also maintaining clinical feasibility. By relying on AUROC, we capture a model's overall discriminative power, and by including AUPRC, we specifically address the model's ability to identify the minority class. Combining these two metrics provides a balanced perspective on model performance and has been shown to improve robustness against domain shifts in clinical settings (Evaluation of domain generalization and adaptation on improving model robustness to temporal dataset shift in clinical medicine, Guo et al., 2022,).

Although we do not explicitly penalize inference time in our final score, we require each submission to process an image in an average of 10 seconds. This aligns with clinical benchmarks, as experienced ophthalmologists can examine a single fundus image in around 9.6 seconds (Clinical Utility of Deep Learning Assistance for Detecting Various Abnormal Findings in Color Retinal Fundus Images: A Reader Study., Shin et al., 2024). Consequently, our

10-second cutoff keeps the challenge grounded in real-world constraints without unduly penalizing teams that meet this reasonable time limit.

In summary, our ranking method balances effectiveness (accuracy in identifying disease) and clinical utility, promoting solutions that not only achieve high performance on class-imbalanced data but also remain feasible in real-world medical workflows.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Missing Data Handling: If a submission fails to produce a prediction for any camera subset, that missing prediction will be treated as a ‘failure’ or assigned zero probability.

Variability of Rankings: We plan to use a bootstrapping approach on each camera subset to generate confidence intervals for the AUC and F1 scores.

Statistical Approach: The Delong test will be performed to compare ROC curves across submissions.

Software: All analyses will be conducted in Python (NumPy, SciPy, scikit-learn) and R (pROC library).

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Bootstrapping is chosen to account for potential class imbalance and to provide robust confidence intervals for each metric. The Delong test is a standard method to statistically compare correlated ROC curves, making it suitable for evaluating multiple submissions on the same datasets.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

The organizers will assess the winning models from multiple perspectives, including ensemble methods, ranking variability, and robustness. The results will be presented in the challenge summary paper. Additionally, the challengeR package (GitHub – DOI:10.1038/s41598-021-82017-6) will be utilized for the analysis.

TASK 2: Classification of Glaucoma and Diabetic Retinopathy with Few-Shot Test Time Adaptation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Accurate classification of retinal diseases—such as glaucoma and diabetic retinopathy—is critical for preventing irreversible vision loss. Although existing screening solutions based on fundus images (e.g., LumineticsCore by Digital Diagnostics) show promise, they often struggle with “unseen” fundus camera images not included in their development. This limitation stems primarily from the continuous influx of new camera models and the varying adoption rates of certain devices. Considering these issues, we propose the Multi-Camera Robust Classification of Fundus Diseases (MuCaRD) challenge, which encourages AI models to work reliably with diverse, previously unseen cameras.

For Task 2, “Classification of Glaucoma and Diabetic Retinopathy with Few-Shot Test Time Adaptation”, the goal is to build a model capable of adapting to new or rare cameras using only a small number of sample images (support set), provided online during the validation and test phases. While the Mediwhale dataset again serves as the primary training and testing resource, the AIREADI dataset supplies both validation and support sets. Because the support set is offered in an online manner, the validation and test data remain hidden from participants—just as in Task 1—ensuring no data leakage occurs.

Given that clinicians in actual clinical settings review and interpret multiple sample images, this task closely mirrors real-world scenarios. Particularly, situations where fundus image data from new cameras exist but cannot be used for training due to restrictions such as data transfer constraints resemble the challenges outlined in Task 2. Through this task, participants will develop models capable of adapting with only a small number of samples (support set), offering practical solutions for handling diverse camera types.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Fundus, Robustness, Multi Camera, Deep learning, few shot adaptation

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Aaron Y. Lee – Department of Ophthalmology, University of Washington, Seattle, Washington

Cecilia S. Lee – Department of Ophthalmology, University of Washington, Seattle, Washington

Dongha Lee – Department of Artificial Intelligence, Yonsei University

Dongjin Nam – Mediwhale; Yonsei University College of Medicine

Geunyoung Lee – Mediwhale

Heeju Ko – Mediwhale

Hyeonmin Kim – Mediwhale

Junseok Park – Mediwhale; Seoul National University College of Medicine

Jungkyung Cho – Mediwhale; Seoul National University College of Medicine

Kai Tzu-iunn Ong – Department of Artificial Intelligence, Yonsei University

Sahil Thakur – Mediwhale

Soojin Hwang – Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Pohang University of Science and Technology

Sungyeon Kim – Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Pohang University of Science and Technology

Taegeun Yoo – Mediwhale

Tyler Hyungtaek Rim – Mediwhale; Duke-NUS Medical School; Singapore Eye Research Institute

Wonhwa Kim – Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Pohang University of Science and Technology

Yongseok Lee – Mediwhale; Yonsei University College of Medicine

Yunnie Cho – Mediwhale; Seoul National University College of Medicine

Yeonwoo Jung – Mediwhale; Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Pohang University of Science and Technology

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Hyeonmin Kim, Mediwhale, kjven0625@mediwhale.com

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

CodaLab (<https://codalab.lisn.upsaclay.fr/>).

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

The challenge platform will be set up once the proposal is accepted.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May not participate

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We intend to award certificates to the top three teams for each task

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The top three performing methods will be publicly announced, and participants will be required to submit documentation detailing their code and methodology. They must also demonstrate reproducibility by providing the datasets used.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Each participant may publish their own papers. However, only the first authors and corresponding authors of the winning teams will be included in the challenge summary paper published by the organizers.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Participants will add their training models and image preprocessing methods to the model.py provided by the organizers and submit it along with the model weights to CodaLab. We encourage the use of MONAI and recommend submitting the code in the form of a MONAI bundle whenever possible to enhance reusability.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

During the validation phase, participants may submit up to two times per day over approximately two months. In the test phase, three submissions will be permitted, and the organizers will select the best result among them. In both phases, participants will submit their inference code and trained model weights for evaluation on the organizers' evaluation server, where the validation and test sets remain completely isolated. For Task 2, a support set will be provided online during both the validation and test phases, allowing participants to perform on-the-fly adaptation without any data leakage.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Registration period: April 1 - June 1, 2025

Release date of training set: June 1, 2025

model for Validation submission period June 1, - August 15, 2025

model for Test submission period: August 15 - August 23, 2025

Winner announcement date: August 30, 2025

Report submission period (for Winner): August 30 - September 15, 2025

Release date of the results: challenge day (October 6 or 10, 2025)

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

AIREADI has already received IRB approval. The AIREADI project is funded by the NIH under award number 1OT2OD032644. The IRB approval for AIREADI can be found here:

https://docs.aireadi.org/v1/Approval_STUDY00016228_Lee_initial.pdf. In addition, another study that will be used in conjunction is currently under IRB review, and all data collection will begin only after IRB approval. We plan to collect data between March and June 2025.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)

- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY (Attribution)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

we will publish the metric calculation code for ranking evaluation. This code will be made available on GitHub and accessible to everyone.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participants are encouraged to publicly share their code to GitHub, and it is mandatory for winning teams to do so.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Some of the challenge organizers are employees of Mediwhale. Once the test phase begins, only the challenge organizers, including those from other institutions, will have access to the test dataset.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Screening

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort includes individuals with diabetic retinopathy and/or glaucoma who have undergone fundoscopic imaging using multiple fundus cameras. Incorporating a variety of commercially available cameras reflects the final biomedical application scenario and ensures broader applicability. Both the World Health Organization (WHO) and the U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) recommend regular eye exams for these conditions, underscoring the importance of applicability across diverse imaging devices.

(<https://www.who.int/europe/publications/i/item/9789289055321>, <https://www.uspreventiveservicestaskforce.org/uspstf/recommendation/primary-open-angle-glaucoma-screening>).

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort consists of a dataset collected from primary care centers and hospitals in South Korea and Cambodia. This dataset includes retinal images of patients diagnosed with glaucoma and/or diabetic retinopathy. The images were captured using a variety of fundus cameras, including the Topcon TRC-NW400, Optomed Aurora handheld fundus camera, Mediworks FC162, Optos Ultra-Wide Fundus, and Canon CR2 models.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Color Fundus Photography(CFP)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Each Color Fundus Photograph is captured with either the optic disk or the fovea as the center

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Data from the AI-READI project ensures balanced representation across disease severity, race/ethnicity, and gender, thereby enhancing the dataset's generalizability and equity. Additionally, the Mediwhale dataset includes patients aged 20 and above from local clinics and hospitals in South Korea and Cambodia, regardless of gender.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The AI-READI project collects data from multiple sites across the United States, ensuring broad representation across disease severity, race/ethnicity, and gender. This includes various data modalities relevant to diabetes management and retinal health. Meanwhile, the Mediwhale dataset consists of fundus images acquired from local clinics and large hospitals in East Asia—specifically South Korea and Cambodia. These retinal images form the basis for diagnosing and studying conditions like glaucoma and diabetic retinopathy in both the target and challenge cohorts.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Screening glaucoma, diabetic retinopathy

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Consistency,Robustness,Sensitivity,Specificity

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Optomed aurora handheld fundus camera

Topcon NW400 fundus camera

Mediworks FC162 camera

Optos Ultra Wide Fundus

Canon CR2 cameras

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Fundus images were captured by experienced ophthalmologists following standardized imaging protocols.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The data for the AI-READI (AI Ready and Equitable Atlas for Diabetes Insights) project was acquired from three major sites across the United States, involving the recruitment of 4,000 participants. These centers ensure a balanced representation across disease severity, race/ethnicity, and gender, thereby enhancing the dataset's generalizability and equity.

Additionally, the Mediwhale dataset comprises retinal images obtained from multiple local clinics and large hospitals in East Asia, including South Korea and Cambodia. Due to Mediwhale's anonymization and data export policies, the dataset sources are limited to South Korea and Cambodia within the East Asian region.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data were collected by specialized ophthalmologists with over five years of experience.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

In this challenge, a “case” refers to a single color fundus photograph along with any associated metadata including the camera name and reference labels for diabetic retinopathy and glaucoma (e.g., presence or absence of each disease). The algorithm must generate a classification for each case, which is then compared against these reference labels.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The entire dataset comprises approximately 400 images from the NW400 camera for training. During the validation phase, 1,000 images will be utilized—200 each from the Topcon NW400, Optomed Aurora, Mediworks FC162, Optos Ultra Wide Fundus, and Canon CR2 cameras. A similar distribution of 1,000 images will be employed for the test phase, also evenly split among these five cameras. The positive rates for glaucoma and diabetic retinopathy are 7% and 6%, respectively. The training and test datasets will originate from Mediwhale, while the validation dataset will include data from both AI-READI and Mediwhale. Unlike Task 1, support sets for the Topcon NW400, Optomed Aurora, Mediworks FC162, Optos Ultra Wide Fundus, and Canon CR2 cameras will be provided together, consisting of image-label pairs with 5 images per camera manufacturer.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The challenge aims to replicate a real-world production environment where variations in camera manufacturers lead to differences in color profiles and image quality. Recognizing that models may be discontinued or replaced (e.g., the transition from Topcon NW400 to NW500), it is crucial to ensure that new models can adapt to these changes. This scenario is common across all data modalities, underscoring the importance of incorporating diverse camera data.

To address this, the dataset includes approximately 400 NW400 images for training—mirroring the training set size of the REFUGE1 challenge. For validation and testing, each set comprises 1,000 images, distributed evenly across five camera models: Topcon NW400, Optomed Aurora, Mediworks FC162, Optos Ultra Wide Fundus, and Canon CR2 (200 images per model). This balanced distribution is designed to enhance model robustness and ensure better generalization to various imaging devices.

Participants are also encouraged to leverage external open datasets, such as Justrags and REFUGE, to bolster their training efforts. By maintaining diversity in the validation and test sets and encouraging the use of varied training data, this dataset reflects the development of adaptable, reliable diagnostic models suitable for production environments.

Additionally, Task 2 includes a support set. Following standard conventions for few-shot learning, the support set will consist of 5 image-label pairs per camera manufacturer.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The data was primarily collected from local primary care hospitals and major hospitals in South Korea and Cambodia, ensuring that it reflects real-world conditions and distributions.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

The data was exclusively gathered from local primary care hospitals and major hospitals in South Korea and Cambodia. It is entirely novel, with no publicly available datasets utilized.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The ground truth was determined by a consensus of two experienced ophthalmologists (and a third if necessary).

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Ophthalmologists were instructed to consider diabetic retinopathy (DR) and glaucoma when reviewing CFP images.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We have two classes of annotators:

A1 - Ophthalmologists with at least five years of professional experience

A2 - Ophthalmologists with at least ten years of professional experience

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The basic annotations of the datasets were meticulously performed by two A1 annotators. If there was a disagreement in these annotations, a third annotation by A2 annotator was brought in to resolve the discrepancy. This process was consistently applied across the training, validation, and test sets to ensure uniformity and reliability in the annotations.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For personal information protection, RGB-formatted CFP images (in .PNG format) were extracted from the original DICOM files.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Since image annotations in this dataset were determined by consensus, one primary source of potential error arises when there is a disagreement between the two A1 annotators. Such discrepancies are resolved by involving an A2 annotator, but minor variability may still remain.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We will evaluate the submitted algorithms primarily using Area Under the ROC Curve (AUROC) and Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve (AUPRC) for each classification task (glaucoma vs. normal, and diabetic retinopathy vs. normal) across multiple fundus cameras. The final ranking for each team will be determined by averaging the AUROC and AUPRC scores for the two diseases.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

In addressing the challenge of class imbalance, we note that glaucoma and diabetic retinopathy each have a relatively low prevalence (about 6–7% in our dataset). While the Area Under the ROC Curve (AUROC) is a widely recognized measure that summarizes performance across all decision thresholds, it can be overly optimistic for imbalanced datasets. Therefore, we also include the Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve (AUPRC), which provides a more detailed view of how well a model identifies true positives across varying thresholds. This is particularly crucial for diseases like glaucoma and diabetic retinopathy, where missed cases can have serious clinical implications. By combining AUROC and AUPRC, as suggested by Evaluation of domain generalization and adaptation on improving model robustness to temporal dataset shift in clinical medicine (Guo et al., 2022), we balance the model's overall discriminative power with its ability to detect the smaller positive class, ensuring a more comprehensive evaluation of both general and minority-class performance.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Each submission will be evaluated on five camera subsets: Topcon NW400, Optomed Aurora, Mediworks FC162, Optos Ultra Wide, and Canon CR2. Specifically, we will compute both the AUROC and AUPRC for the glaucoma classification and the diabetic retinopathy classification tasks for each subset. We then average these two metrics to derive a single camera-specific score per disease, and finally average across diseases. The overall score for each submission is obtained by further averaging these camera-specific scores across all five subsets. Submissions will be ranked in descending order based on this final overall score.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If a submission is incomplete, it will not be counted, and participants will be allowed to resubmit. In cases of missing results, an error message will be provided, automatically notifying participants of the required elements as part of the error feedback.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Our primary objective is to ensure robust classification performance in the context of class imbalance while also maintaining clinical feasibility. By relying on AUROC, we capture a model's overall discriminative power, and by including AUPRC, we specifically address the model's ability to identify the minority class. Combining these two

metrics provides a balanced perspective on model performance and has been shown to improve robustness against domain shifts in clinical settings (Evaluation of domain generalization and adaptation on improving model robustness to temporal dataset shift in clinical medicine, Guo et al., 2022,).

Although we do not explicitly penalize inference time in our final score, we require each submission to process an image in an average of 10 seconds. This aligns with clinical benchmarks, as experienced ophthalmologists can examine a single fundus image in around 9.6 seconds (Clinical Utility of Deep Learning Assistance for Detecting Various Abnormal Findings in Color Retinal Fundus Images: A Reader Study., Shin et al., 2024). Consequently, our 10-second cutoff keeps the challenge grounded in real-world constraints without unduly penalizing teams that meet this reasonable time limit.

In summary, our ranking method balances effectiveness (accuracy in identifying disease) and clinical utility, promoting solutions that not only achieve high performance on class-imbalanced data but also remain feasible in real-world medical workflows.

Statistical analyses

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- description of the missing data handling,
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Missing Data Handling: If a submission fails to produce a prediction for any camera subset, that missing prediction will be treated as a 'failure' or assigned zero probability.

Variability of Rankings: We plan to use a bootstrapping approach on each camera subset to generate confidence intervals for the AUC and F1 scores.

Statistical Approach: The Delong test will be performed to compare ROC curves across submissions.

Software: All analyses will be conducted in Python (NumPy, SciPy, scikit-learn) and R (pROC library).

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Bootstrapping is chosen to account for potential class imbalance and to provide robust confidence intervals for each metric. The Delong test is a standard method to statistically compare correlated ROC curves, making it suitable for evaluating multiple submissions on the same datasets.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

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The organizers will assess the winning models from multiple perspectives, including ensemble methods, ranking variability, and robustness. The results will be presented in the challenge summary paper. Additionally, the challengeR package (GitHub – DOI:10.1038/s41598-021-82017-6) will be utilized for the analysis.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

AIREADI is a dataset comprising heterogeneous multimodal data that holds great academic value. We intend to use it to host a challenge.

paper link : <https://www.nature.com/articles/s42255-024-01165-x>

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42255-024-01165-x>

website : <https://aireadi.org/publications>

[1] Guo, L. L., Pfohl, S. R., Fries, J., Johnson, A. E. W., Posada, J., Aftandilian, C., Shah, N., & Sung, L. (2022). Evaluation of domain generalization and adaptation on improving model robustness to temporal dataset shift in clinical medicine. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), 2726.

[2] Shin, J. Y., Son, J., Kong, S. T., Park, J., Park, B., Park, K. H., Jung, K.-H., & Park, S. J. (2024). Clinical Utility of Deep Learning Assistance for Detecting Various Abnormal Findings in Color Retinal Fundus Images: A Reader Study. *Translational Vision Science & Technology*, 13(10), 34.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A